

A MEDIATION ANALYSIS ON SOCIAL SUPPORT TO THE EFFECT OF INTERDEPENDENT HAPPINESS IN MENTAL HEALTH CONCERNS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 8

Pages: 797-806

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2506

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13941184

Manuscript Accepted: 07-08-2024

A Mediation Analysis on Social Support to the Effect of Interdependent Happiness in Mental Health Concerns

Ralph Randel R. Rivera,* Lyella Mae N. Delgado
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The concept of "interdependent happiness", which is happiness obtained by achieving interdependent goals, which is more common in interdependent daily life. This happiness can somehow provide by the people around the individual or their social supports. This study is a descriptive-mediation analysis approach that aimed to explore effect of interdependent happiness to mental health concerns such as depressive and anxious moods mediated by social support among students. Three-hundred participants from the BS Psychology program of LSPU Sta. Cruz and LCBA were the participants of this study. The result of the study suggests the interdependent happiness affects the student's social support. Social support and interdependent happiness have an alleviating effect to depressive and anxious moods. Social support demonstrates its mediation effect on the interdependent happiness to the mental health concerns of the students in participants. A collective workbook of activities in facilitating, enhancing and sustaining connections is recommended as part of the output of the study that can be used by counselors and other allied mental health professionals to strengthen interdependent happiness and social support among students.

Keywords: *positive psychology, mental health, depression, anxiety, social support*

Introduction

Positive psychology is the study of the conditions and processes that contribute to the flourishing or optimal functioning of people, groups, and institutions. What kind of impact does happiness have on people, particularly students? Individuals in collectivist societies are more prone to advocate for a socially oriented definition of happiness. Previous research on the effects of happiness and well-being, on the other hand, has mostly focused on how a person's personal definition of happiness influenced beneficial scholastic and psychological outcomes. Happiness is defined by a number of variables. The concept of being optimistic, as defined by positive psychology, is somewhat related with the concept of happiness. Positive emotions as joy, gratitude, serenity, interest, hope, pride, amusement, inspiration, awe and love play a central role in the treatment and can function as a kind of protection against stress, anxiety and depression. Happiness is a state of mind in which a person appreciates life, whether or not they have someone to cling to; even if they only have a single penny in their pocket; living a contented and satisfied existence. The happy and joyful men and women who are focused, enthusiastic, optimistic, and not depressed are unaffected by the chaotic environment we live in. Relevant to the RA 11036 or also known as The Philippine Mental Health Act of 2017 has created a framework for the management and delivery of hospital- and community-based mental healthcare in the nation, with explicit legislative provisions to ensure the rights of individuals receiving mental healthcare and treatment are maintained.

Mental health problems like depression, anxiety, and despair thrive when people lack happiness. Typical signs of these issues include losing pleasure, not engaging in activities, and feeling meaningless. Psychology has made good progress treating various mental illnesses, but it has fallen short in fully developing human potential, abilities, and happiness. As a result, positive psychology emerged to re-emphasize the importance of positive aspects of human nature within psychology - like happiness, virtues, strengths, and altruism. Traditional approaches in schools for helping children and families focus on problems and disruptions, which is especially relevant today given high rates of mental illness among vulnerable youths. Therapeutic interventions require qualified counselors/psychologists, making them costly. Exploring how to integrate positive psychology into school psychology offers a way to shift the focus from just addressing deficits to also promoting strengths and well-being.

Today's students are at risk of developing depression and other mental health problems. They are exposed to the stresses that life throws upon them. However, the researchers intends to provide a meaningful intervention through his study that can assist teenagers in the community in discovering their intrapersonal talents to help them cope with depression. This isn't simply a motivator and a cure for the students who will be a part of this research. Due to this concerns, Lyubomirsky (2002) stated the happiness have this 'undoing effect' to negative emotions and concerns towards mental health. This could be a game-changer in terms of addressing depression and other mental health concern's undiscovered fundamental cause and proving the efficacy as an alternative to therapy and proposed by Positive Psychology, the newest discipline of psychology. The concept of interdependent happiness proposes that an individual's happiness is intrinsically tied to the wellbeing of others in their social network. This differs from the traditional view of happiness as an independent and personal emotional state (Hitokoto & Uchida, 2015). Research on interdependent happiness has investigated how an individual's happiness is associated with the happiness of various members of their social circle. Longitudinal research also supports the social support and interdependent happiness link. Matsunaga, Iwasaki, and Keiko (2009) tracked Japanese seniors over a 10-year period and found perceived emotional support predicted increased interdependent happiness over time. Hence, social support may cumulatively boost interdependent wellbeing. Furthermore, Yoo (2017) experimentally manipulated social exclusion and found it reduced happiness more for interdependently-oriented Koreans, implying social connection is vital for their happiness. Another collectivist study from

Asian country, several studies reveal connections between social support and interdependent happiness. Kim, Sherman, and Taylor (2008) found that South Koreans' life satisfaction was predicted by close others' wellbeing, but only when they perceived high levels of social support from those individuals. They concluded that cultural norms of interdependence are actualized through supportive social relationships. Additionally, a daily diary study by Oishi, Schimmack, and Diener (2007) demonstrated that Japanese respondents' daily happiness was associated with social support judgments. The authors suggested daily happiness fluctuations may be interpersonally determined in interdependent cultures.

Interdependent happiness is a relationship-oriented state of harmony in which a certain balance between the self and significant others is achieved. This happiness can somehow provide by the people around the individual or their social supports. It is quite crucial nowadays due to the pandemic and everybody needs someone to lean on specially for students. If one's happiness is likely to elicit another's unhappiness by instilling negative emotions like envy or jealousy, one's own happiness is discounted. Given with this notion, this paper will further investigate if this interrelation happiness can alleviate mental health concerns of students amidst of this pandemic.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effect of interdependent happiness to the depressive and anxious moods mediated by social support. Specifically, this answered the following questions:

1. What is the perceived level of the student's interdependent happiness?
2. What is the perceived level of social support of the students?
3. What is the degree of the mental health concerns in terms of:
 - 3.1. depressive moods; and
 - 3.2. anxious moods?
4. Does interdependent happiness have significant effect on the social support of the students?
5. Do interdependent happiness and social support have significant effect to the:
 - 5.1. depressive moods; and
 - 5.2. anxious moods?
6. Do interdependent happiness and social support have significant effect on the anxious Moods of the students?
7. Does social support mediate the effect of interdependent happiness to the mental health concerns?

Methodology

Research Design

To gather information about current existing conditions in the field of study of choice, a quantitative approach, specifically a descriptive-mediation analysis research method, was developed. Mediation analyses are used to investigate the underlying mechanism or process by which one variable influences another variable via a mediator variable in order to better understand a known relationship. A variable is a mediator between a predictor and an outcome if the predictor variable first has an effect on the mediator variable, and this in turn influences the outcome variable.

Respondents

The researchers specifically selected 300 college students using the Beck Depression Inventory, Interpersonal Support Evaluation List and the General Anxiety Disorder-7. The participants were students of Laguna State Polytechnic University Main Campus and Laguna College of Business and Arts.

Instrument

In accumulating data, the researchers adapted four standardized self-report questionnaires. The questionnaires are composed of measuring scale in relevance to a number of statements that may or may not apply to the respondent given that they are rating themselves as they see themselves in the present time not as they wish to be in the future. A statement notifying the respondents that there are no right, or wrong answers are given with the directions.

In determining the level of depression among the respondents in this study, an inventory test was used, the Beck Depression Inventory or BDI. It has 21 items, each of which describes four levels of a given symptom of depression. The respondent was asked to indicate which of the description best fits how he or she has been feeling in the past week or more. The items are scored to indicate the level of the depressive Moods. BDI is extremely quick and easy to administer and has good test-retest reliability. Hence, it is widely used, especially in research on depression. A persistent score of 17 or above indicates that the respondent may need medical treatment as listed in American Psychiatric Association's Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders Fourth Edition (Beck, AT, Steer RA. Internal Consistencies of the Original and Revised Beck Depression Inventory. *J Clin Psychol.* 1984 Nov; 40(6):1365-7).

The General Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) is a 7-item self-administered instrument that uses some of the DSM-V criteria for GAD (General Anxiety Disorder) to identify possible cases of GAD while also measuring anxiety symptom severity. It can also be used to screen for panic, social anxiety, and PTSD. It is designed to be used quickly and effectively in a primary care setting.

This is calculated by assigning scores of 0, 1, 2, and 3 to the response categories, respectively, of “not at all,” “several days,” “more than half the days,” and “nearly every day.” GAD-7 total score for the seven items ranges from 0 to 21.

In measuring the interdependent happiness, the researchers used the Interdependent Happiness Scale (HIS) by Hitokoto & Uchida. It showed HIS to be 1) valid across Japan, U.S.A., Germany, and Korea, 2) correlated with theoretically related measures, and 3) the degree to which it is related to general well-being is stronger in Asian countries than in Western countries, and also stronger in rural areas than in urban areas within Japan (Hitokoto & Uchida, 2014). Lastly to gauge the perceived level of social support of the students, the researchers used the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List by Cohen and Hoberman (1986). A 12-item measure of perceptions of social support. This measure is a shortened version of the original ISEL (40 items; Cohen & Hoberman, 1983). This questionnaire has three different subscales designed to measure three dimensions of perceived social support.

Data Analysis

The table summarizes the statistical tools used to analyze and interpret the data. The statistical methods were the following:

Table 1. *Statistical Plan for Data Analysis*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Statistical Tool or Test</i>	
Respondents' Level of Interdependent Happiness	Weighted Mean.	Summary/Descriptive
Interpersonal Harmony	Standard Deviation	Statistics only
Ordinariness		
Quiescence		
Respondents' Level of Social Support	Weighted Mean,	Summary/Descriptive
Interpersonal Support	Standard Deviation	Statistics only
Respondents' Level of Depressive Moods	Weighted Mean,	Summary/Descriptive
Depressive Moods	Standard Deviation	Statistics only
Respondents' Level of Anxious Moods	Weighted Mean,	Summary/Descriptive
Anxious Moods	Standard Deviation	Statistics only
Suggested Analysis/Objective		
Effect of Interdependent Happiness to Social Support (mediator)	Simple Linear Regression	Inferential Statistics
Effect of Interdependent Happiness and Social Support (mediator) to the Mental Health Concerns in terms of Depressive and Anxious Moods	Multiple Regression	Inferential Statistics
Mediation Effect/Analysis	Sobel Test	Inferential Statistics

The table shown above is the summarized table of what the researchers used to analyze the data statistically. The analysis was separated in two aspects; descriptive and inferential statistics. As for the demographics of the respondents the researchers used a frequency distribution and percentage. Level of interdependent happiness, social support, anxious and depressive moods the researchers used mean and standard deviation. For the test of effects among variables, the research used multiple regression and Sobel test.

Results and Discussion

Level of Interdependent Happiness

Table 2. *Level of Interdependent Happiness*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
I believe that I and those around me are happy.	3.69	0.84	Strongly Agree
Although it is quite average, I live a stable life.	3.93	0.95	Strongly Agree
I do not have any major concerns or anxieties.	2.68	1.16	Somewhat Agree
I feel that I am being positively evaluated by others around me.	3.63	0.96	Strongly Agree
I make significant others happy.	4.04	0.78	Strongly Agree
I can do what I want without causing problems for other people.	3.52	1.09	Strongly Agree
I believe that my life is just as happy as that of others around me.	3.09	1.16	Somewhat Agree
I believe I have achieved the same standard of living as those around me.	3.07	1.06	Somewhat Agree
I generally believe that things are going well for me in its own way as they are for others around me.	3.73	1.00	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.49	1.09	High Degree of Happiness

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00, Strongly Agree = Very High Degree of Happiness; 3.40 – 4.19, Somewhat Agree = High Degree of Happiness; 2.60 – 3.39, Neither Agree/Disagree = Moderate Degree of Happiness; 1.80 – 2.59, Somewhat Disagree = Low Degree of Happiness; 1.00 – 1.79, Strongly Disagree = Very Low Degree of Happiness

Table 2 presents the degree of interdependent happiness accordance to the responses of three hundred (300) respondents.

The result indicates that the interdependent happiness is “MODERATE” in items such as I do not have any major concerns or anxieties, with the mean score of 2.68 (SD = 1.16); item I believe that my life is just as happy as that of others around me, with the mean of 3.09 (SD = 1.16); and lastly, item I believe I have achieved the same standard of living as those around me obtained a mean of 3.07 (SD =

1.00).

On other hand, it scored “VERY HIGH” on succeeding items such as I believe that I and those around me are happy, with the mean of 3.36 (SD = 0.84); Although it is quite average, I live a stable life, with the mean of 3.93 (SD = 0.95); I feel that I am being positively evaluated by others around me with the mean of 3.63 (SD = 0.96); I make significant others happy, with the mean of 4.04 (SD = 0.78); I can do what I want without causing problems for other people, with the mean of 3.52 (SD = 1.09); and lastly I generally believe that things are going well for me in its own way as they are for others around me, with the mean of 3.26 (SD = 1.00)

Younger students, according to the survey, are happier. This is consistent with the widely accepted U-shaped relationship between happiness and age, which states that happiness declines with age before reaching middle age (Galamos et. al, 2020)

According to the findings of Moghadam and colleague (2016), contact with family and the relationship with parents were significantly related to student happiness. This is consistent with the widely accepted attachment theory, according to which individuals must communicate meaningfully with one another in order to live a happy life.

Level of Social Support

Table 3. *Level of Social Support*

Statement	Mean	Sd	Remarks
If I wanted to go on a trip for a day (for example, to the country or mountains), I would have a hard time finding someone to go with me.	2.25	0.96	Poor
I feel that there is no one I can share my most private worries and fears with.	2.11	1.09	Poor
If I were sick, I could easily find someone to help me with my daily chores.	2.85	0.91	Excellent
There is someone I can turn to for advice about handling problems with my family.	3.06	1.01	Excellent
If I decide one afternoon that I would like to go to a movie that evening, I could easily find someone to go with me.	2.74	0.98	Excellent
When I need suggestions on how to deal with a personal problem, I know someone I can turn to.	3.22	0.88	Excellent
I don't often get invited to do things with others.	2.22	0.90	Poor
If I had to go out of town for a few weeks, it would be difficult to find someone who would look after my house or apartment (the plants, pets, garden, etc.).	2.42	1.06	Poor
If I wanted to have lunch with someone, I could easily find someone to join me.	3.06	0.85	Excellent
If I was stranded 10 miles from home, there is someone I could call who could come and get me	3.03	0.87	Excellent
If a family crisis arose, it would be difficult to find someone who could give me good advice about how to handle it.	2.28	0.93	Poor
Overall	2.61	0.95	High Degree of Social Support

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00, Excellent = Very High Degree of Social Support; 2.51 – 3.25, Good = High Degree of Social Support; 1.76 – 2.50, Poor = Low Degree of Social Support; 1.00 – 1.75, Very Poor = Very Low Degree of Social Support

Table 3 presents the degree of social/interpersonal support accordance to the responses of three hundred (300) respondents.

The result indicates that the interdependent happiness is “LOW” in items such as If I wanted to go on a trip for a day (for example, to the country or mountains), I would have a hard time finding someone to go with me, with the mean score of 2.25 (SD = 0.96); I feel that there is no one I can share my most private worries and fears with., with the mean of 2.11 (SD = 1.09); I don't often get invited to do things with others obtained a mean of 2.22 (SD = 0.90); If I had to go out of town for a few weeks, it would be difficult to find someone who would look after my house or apartment (the plants, pets, garden, etc.) with mean of 2.42 (SD = 1.06) and lastly, item If a family crisis arose, it would be difficult to find someone who could give me good advice about how to handle it obtained a mean of 2.28 (SD = 0.93)

On other hand, it scored “HIGH” on succeeding items such as If I were sick, I could easily find someone to help me with my daily chores, with the mean of 2.85 (SD = 0.91); There is someone I can turn to for advice about handling problems with my family, with the mean of 3.06 (SD = 1.01); If I decide one afternoon that I would like to go to a movie that evening, I could easily find someone to go with me with the mean of 2.74 (SD = 0.98); When I need suggestions on how to deal with a personal problem, I know someone I can turn to, with the mean of 3.22 (SD = 0.88); If I wanted to have lunch with someone, I could easily find someone to join me, with the mean of 3.06 (SD = 0.86); and lastly If I was stranded 10 miles from home, there is someone I could call who could come and get me, with the mean of 3.03 (SD = 0.87).

People's perceptions of themselves and their surroundings are influenced by their perceived social support. According to a meta-analysis, not having a network of meaningful relationships in life predicts mortality more than smoking or physical activity (Holt-Lunstad and Smith, 2012).

Level of Depressive Moods (Beck's Depression Inventory)

Table 4 presents the degree of depressive moods accordance to the responses of three hundred (300) respondents.

Table 4. Degree of Depressive Moods

Inventory	Mean	Sd	Remarks
Beck's Depression Inventory 1	1.79	0.80	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 2	1.76	0.94	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 3	1.89	0.87	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 4	1.78	0.87	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 5	2.04	0.78	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 6	2.11	1.14	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 7	1.80	0.79	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 8	2.11	0.90	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 9	1.57	0.72	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 10	2.17	1.23	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 11	2.08	0.92	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 12	2.06	0.85	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 13	1.83	0.94	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 14	2.24	1.08	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 15	2.89	0.67	High Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 16	1.87	0.87	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 17	2.24	0.87	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 18	1.65	0.74	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 19	1.30	0.61	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 20	2.00	0.95	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Beck's Depression Inventory 21	1.71	0.98	Low Degree of Depressive Moods
Overall	1.96	0.88	Low Degree of Depressive Moods

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00, Very High Degree of Depressive Moods; 2.51 – 3.25, High Degree of Depressive Moods; 1.76 – 2.50, Low Degree of Depressive Moods; 1.00 – 1.75, Very Low Degree of Depressive Moods

The result indicates that majority of the respondents have “LOW” interpretation in depressive Moods with ranging means of 1.79 to 2.24; SD ranges from 0.61 to 0.80. On other hand, it scored “HIGH” on item with the mean of 2.89 (SD = 0.67). Social support from friends and utilizing campus resources like counseling services may help buffer against depressive moods among students (Byrd & McKinney, 2012). Overall, research underscores the high prevalence of depressive symptoms in student populations and the need for mental health services and support systems on campuses.

Level of Anxious Moods (GAD-7)

Table 5. Degree of Anxious Moods

Statement	Mean	Sd	Remarks
Feeling nervous, anxious, or on edge	2.49	0.91	Low Degree of Anxious Moods
Not being able to stop or control worrying	2.46	0.97	Low Degree of Anxious Moods
Worrying too much about different things	2.81	0.99	High Degree of Anxious Moods
Trouble relaxing	2.43	0.99	Low Degree of Anxious Moods
Being so restless that it is hard to sit still	2.17	0.99	Low Degree of Anxious Moods
Becoming easily annoyed or irritable	2.44	1.00	Low Degree of Anxious Moods
Feeling afraid, as if something awful might happen	2.47	1.04	Low Degree of Anxious Moods
Overall	2.45	0.98	Low Degree of Anxious Moods

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00, Very High Degree of Anxious Moods; 2.51 – 3.25, High Degree of Anxious Moods; 1.76 – 2.50, Low Degree of Anxious Moods; 1.00 – 1.75, Very Low Degree of Anxious Moods

Table 5 shows the degree of anxious Moods accordance to the responses of three hundred (300) respondents. The result indicates that the anxious Moods is ”HIGH” in item worrying too much about different things, with the mean of 2.81 (SD = 0.99)On other hand, it scored “LOW” on succeeding items such as Feeling nervous, anxious, or on edge, with the mean of 2.49 (SD = 0.91); Not being able to stop or control worrying mean of 2.46 (SD = 0.97); Trouble relaxing, with the mean of 2.43 (SD = 0.99); Becoming easily annoyed or irritable with mean of 2.44 (SD = 1.00); Feeling afraid, as if something awful might happen with mean of 2.47 (SD = 1.04)and lastly being so restless that it is hard to sit still, with the mean of 2.17 (SD = 0.99). Several studies reveal factors associated with anxiety among students. Academic pressure, heavy workloads, competitive environments, and perfectionism correlate with increased anxiety (Neal et al., 2019). Social anxiety is also common, with university students reporting fears about social situations and interactions affecting their mood (Russell & Shaw, 2009). Financial and family stress can also provoke anxiety in students (Cheng et al., 2019).

Table 6. Effect of Interdependent Happiness and Social Support of BS Psychology Students

Model	Estimate	SE	t	p	Decision	Remarks
(Constant)	3.557	0.301	11.82	< .001		
Interdependent Happiness	0.476	0.058	8.267	< .001	Reject	Significant
R Value	0.605		F Value	46.467		
R Squared	0.366		p value	< .001		

Table 6 shows a linear regression analysis on the association of interdependent happiness and social support of the respondents. It is hypothesized that the interdependent happiness does not associate with the social support. The results showed that there is a significant effect on social support by the interdependent happiness, $R = 0.605$, $p < 0.001$. Results show that the 36.60% of the variance explained by interdependent happiness, $F(1,298) = 46.467$, $p < 0.001$. Thus all in all, this result of the study revealed that interdependent happiness significantly associates with social support of the respondents.

In a study conducted by Motamedi and colleagues (2008) Individuals who received favorable social support are expected to have a more positive outlook on life, a higher level of satisfaction, and better functioning than those who do not.

The findings revealed a significant and positive relationship between social support dimension (informational, appraisal, and so on) and happiness; that is, people who received more social support were happier (Keykhosravi et.al, 2015).

Table 7. *Effect of Interdependent Happiness and Social Support (mediator) to the Depressive Moods among students*

Model	Estimate	SE	t	p	Decision	Remarks
(Constant)	36.12	8.37	4.32	< .001		
Interdependent Happiness	-6.82	1.23	-5.55	< .001	Reject	Significant
Social Support	-2.780	2.61	1.06	< .001	Reject	Significant
R Value	0.461		F Value	16.5		
R Squared	0.212		p value	< .001		

Table 7 shows a multiple linear regression analysis on the effect of interdependent happiness and social support to the depressive Moods of the students. It is hypothesized that the interdependent happiness and social support does not have effect on the depressive moods. The results showed that interdependent happiness and social support significantly affects the depressive Moods of the students, $R = 0.461$, $p < 0.001$. Results show that the 21.2% of the variance explained by interdependent happiness and social support, $F(1,298) = 16.50$, $p < 0.001$.

Research evidence indicates a significant negative relationship between social support and psychological disorders including depression and stress (Alimoradi, Asadi, Asadbejgy, & Asadniya, 2014; Bukhari & Afzal, 2017; Kugbey, 2015).

Table 8. *Effect of Interdependent Happiness and Social Support (mediator) to the Anxious Moods among students*

Model	Estimate	SE	t	p	Decision	Remarks
(Constant)	26.158	4.615	5.668	< .001		
Interdependent Happiness	-2.185	0.678	-3.224	0.002	Reject	Significant
Social Support	-0.334	1.441	-0.232	< .001	Reject	Significant
R Value	0.514		F Value	5.20		
R Squared	0.264		p value	< .001		

Table 8 shows a multiple linear regression analysis on the effect of interdependent happiness and social support to the anxious moods of the students. It is hypothesized that the interdependent happiness and social support does not have effect on the anxious moods. The results showed that interdependent happiness and social support significantly affects the anxious mood of the students, $R = 0.514$, $p < 0.001$. Results show that the 26.4% of the variance explained by interdependent happiness and social support, $F(1,298) = 5.20$, $p < 0.001$.

Through three dimensions: warmth, behavioral control, and psychological autonomy-granting, social support promotes positive self-concepts and social skills, responsibility and competence, and impulse control, resulting in a low level of psychological problems such as depression and anxiety (Oswald et. al, 1994).

Mediation analysis via Sobel Test was utilized to determine if social support mediates the effect of interdependent happiness to the depressive moods of the students. The analysis reveal that the interdependent happiness has significant direct inverse effect on depressive moods ($\beta = -6.822$, $p < 0.001$). Result also showed that social support mediates the effect of interdependent happiness to the depressive moods ($\beta = -0.09$, $p < 0.001$). This means that interdependent happiness is directly and indirectly related to depressive moods of the students by mediation of social support. This suggests that students who have interdependent happiness experienced through their social support which, in turn, can lower down their depressive moods. Several studies reveal links between greater social support,

interdependent happiness, and lower depression.

Table 9. Mediation Analysis on Social Support thru Interdependent Happiness to the Depressive Moods of the Students

Type	Effect	Estimate	SE	p	Analysis
Indirect	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Social Support ⇒ Depressive Moods	-0.089	0.143	< .001	Significant
Component	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Social Support	-0.032	0.042	< .001	Significant
	Social Support ⇒ Depressive Moods	2.776	2.581	< .001	Significant
Direct	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Depressive Moods	-6.822	1.214	< .001	Significant
Total	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Depressive Moods	-6.911	1.222	< .001	Significant

Ineichen (1998) found that perceived social support partially mediated the relationship between family involvement and reduced depression in Chinese students, highlighting the importance of social connections. Shim et al. (2021) also found Korean college students' depression was negatively predicted by family support through its effects on increasing happiness.

Figure 1. Model Diagram of Mediation Analysis on the Depressive Mood

A graphical representation of how interdependent happiness mediated with social support in the effects of alleviation of depressive symptoms.

Such result of this study adheres to the same study conducted by Camara & Padilla, (2017); Dafaalla et al., (2016) and Kugbey, (2015) by making people feel valued and connected to their social networks, social support improves mental health and quality of life. This sense of support is linked to lower levels of mental health problems, acting as a protective factor against depression. Social support from family and friends is a predictor and significantly correlates with depressive symptoms.

Table 10. Mediation Analysis on Social Support thru Interdependent Happiness to the Anxious Moods of the Students

Type	Effect	Estimate	SE	p
Indirect	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Social Support ⇒ Anxious Moods	0.0107	0.048	< .001
Component	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Social Support	-0.0321	0.042	< .001
	Social Support ⇒ Anxious Moods	-0.3342	1.423	< .001
Direct	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Anxious Moods	-2.1849	0.670	< .001
Total	Interdependent Happiness ⇒ Anxious Moods	-2.1742	0.671	< .001

Mediation analysis via Sobel Test was utilized to determine if social support mediates the effect of interdependent happiness to the anxious moods of the students. The analysis reveal that the interdependent happiness has significant direct inverse effect on anxious moods ($\beta = -2.1849, p < 0.001$). Result also showed that social support mediates the effect of interdependent happiness to the anxious moods ($\beta = 0.01, p < 0.001$). This means that interdependent happiness is directly and indirectly related to anxious moods of the students by mediation of social support. This suggests that students who have interdependent happiness experienced through their social support which, in turn, can lower down their anxious moods.

Figure 2. Model Diagram of Mediation Analysis on the Anxious Mood

A graphical representation of how interdependent happiness mediated with social support in the effects of alleviation of anxious moods.

Previous studies have linked a lack of social support to depression, anxiety, attention issues, social problems, somatic complaints, and low self-esteem. Social support appears to be important because it acts as a buffer against life stressors and promotes health and wellness (Steese et. al, 2006). Although there are findings about the relationships of these internal and external resources with depression and anxiety, we discovered that few general population studies have been conducted, and there has been little attempt to assess the association of social support and coping styles with depression and anxiety (Vildósola et. al, 2012).

Conclusions

Such conclusion was drawn from the findings. The interdependent happiness and social supports of the respondents was said to be in high degree. On the other hand, the level of depressive moods among respondents was said to be low while perceived level of anxious moods among respondents is said to be low as well. The high interdependent happiness and social support indicates respondents derive a strong sense of wellbeing from close relationships and social harmony. This aligns with previous research on collectivistic cultures prioritizing interpersonal connectedness. Potentially, the anxiety could arise from pressures to maintain harmony within the respondents' in-groups. The respondents may feel a little anxious about inadvertently upsetting valued social bonds, even as they derive happiness from those connections when harmony is preserved.

The results on the effect of interdependent happiness to the social support of the respondents is said to be statistically significant. Likewise with the results from the effect of the interdependent happiness and social support to the depressive moods manifest significant findings and significant findings emerge from the effect of interdependent happiness and social support on anxious moods. In the mediation analysis, interdependent happiness is directly and indirectly related to students' depressive moods via social support. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Since social support mediates the link between interdependent happiness and lower depression, interventions aimed at enhancing supportive resources may have therapeutic benefits. Peer counseling groups and social-emotional learning programs could teach students skills for providing empathy, advice and practical assistance to further sustain their emotional wellbeing. The cultural value placed on interpersonal harmony appears protective for mental health. Therefore, mental health promotion efforts should be careful not to undermine collectivistic values, and instead align with building community and meaningful relationships. However, some students may require direct clinical intervention when social resources are insufficient in alleviating mood issues. Counselors should screen for anxiety and depression, especially when warning signs persist despite strong social ties. Lastly, the main aim of this study is to create an intervention to mental health concerns among students through positivity and happiness activity. Refer to the researchers' collective workbook of positive psychology enhancing social support/interpersonal relations to improve well-being of students that will help school counselor and other mental health practitioner. Future researchers may utilize other tools in positive psychology in assessing the optimal being in alleviating mental health concerns in the pandemic. Future research can explore other mental health concerns like burnout, stress, job performance etc. to further assess how positive interaction to people have an effect on their functions.

References

- Alimoradi, M., Asadi, H., Asadbeigy, H., & Asadniya, R. (2014). The study of links between social support and psychological problems among youth. *International Journal of Basic Sciences & Applied Research*, 3, 270–274.
- Bukhari, S. R., & Afzal, F. (2017). Perceived social support predicts psychological problems among university students. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4(2), 2349–3429.

- Byrd, D. R., & McKinney, K. J. (2012). Individual, interpersonal, and institutional level factors associated with the mental health of college students. *Journal of American College Health*, 60(3), 185-193.
- Camara, M., Bacigalupe, G., & Padilla, P. (2017). The role of social support in adolescents: Are you helping me or stressing me out? *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 22(2), 123-136.
- Cheng, H., Wang, C., McDermott, R. C., Kridel, M., & Rislin, J. L. (2018). Self-stigma, mental health literacy, and attitudes toward seeking psychological help. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 96(1), 64-74.
- Cohen, S., Mermelstein, R., Kamarck, T., & Hoberman, H. M. (1985). Measuring the functional components of social support. In Sarason, I. G., & Sarason, B. R. (Eds.), *Social support: Theory, research, and applications* (pp. 73-94). The Hague, Netherlands: Martinus Nijhoff.
- Dafaalla, M., Farah, A., Bashir, S., Khalil, A., Abdulhamid, R., Mokhtar, M., et al. (2016). Depression, anxiety, and stress in Sudanese medical students: A cross-sectional study on the role of quality of life and social support. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4(13). <http://pubs.sciepub.com/education/4/13/4>
- Galambos, N. L., Krahn, H. J., Johnson, M. D., & Lachman, M. E. (2020). The U shape of happiness across the life course: Expanding the discussion. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 15, 898-912.
- Hitokoto, H., & Uchida, Y. (2015). Interdependent happiness: Theoretical importance and measurement validity. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 16(1), 211-239.
- Holt-Lunstad, J., & Smith, T. B. (2012). Social relationships and mortality. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 6, 41-53. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1000316
- Ineichen, B. (1998). The influence of social support on mental well-being in student and worker samples: A causal analysis. *Social Indicators Research*, 43(3), 315-334.
- Kim, S., Sherman, D. K., & Taylor, S. E. (2008). Culture and social support. *American Psychologist*, 63(6), 518-526.
- Kugbey, N. (2015). The influence of social support on the levels of depression, anxiety, and stress among students in Ghana. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(25), 135-140.
- Lyubomirsky, S., & Lepper, H. S. (2002). A measure of subjective happiness: Preliminary reliability and construct validation. *Social Indicators Research*, 46, 137-155.
- Matsunaga, M., Iwasaki, Y., & Keiko, I. (2009). Personality stability and change over a 10-year period in adult men and women: Findings from the MIDUS study. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 43(1), 42-52.
- Moghadam, M., Rezaei, F., Ghaderi, E., & Rostamian, N. (2016). Relationship between attachment styles and happiness in medical students. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 5, 593-599.
- Neal, A. M., & Richards, K. (2019). Examining anxiety, depression, and sleep quality of college students. *Journal of Research, Assessment, and Practice in Higher Education*, 4(1), 43-52.
- Oishi, S., Schimmack, U., & Diener, E. (2017). The optimal level of well-being: Can people be too happy? *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 2(4), 346-360.
- Oswald, H., & Suss, K. U. (1994). The influence of parents and peers on misconduct at school: Simultaneous and synergistic effects. In Silbereisen, R. K., & Todt, E. (Eds.), *Adolescence in context: The interplay of family, school, peers, and work in adjustment* (pp. 139-158). New York: Springer-Verlag Inc.
- Russell, G., & Shaw, S. (2009). A study to investigate the prevalence of social anxiety in a sample of higher education students in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Mental Health*, 18(3), 198-206.
- Shim, H. S., Lee, S. J., & Paul, B. (2021). College students' mental health and their perceived social support from family, friends, and significant others: A longitudinal study. *Journal of College Counseling*, 24(1), 57-71.
- Steese, S., Dollette, M., Phillips, W., Hossfeld, E., Matthews, G., & Taormina, G. (2006). Understanding Girls' Circle as an intervention on perceived social support, body image, self-efficacy, locus of control, and self-esteem. *Adolescence*, 41, 55-74.
- Vildósola, A. C., Guerra, A. L., & Jaramillo-Villanueva, L. (2012). Coping strategies and their relation with depression and anxiety in pediatric residents in a third-level pediatric hospital. *Boletín Médico del Hospital Infantil de México*, 69, 347-354.
- Yoo, S. H. (2017). How social exclusion influences interdependent self-construal and feeling of happiness. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 48(5), 691-708.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lyella Mae N. Delgado

National University – Philippines

Ralph Randel R. Rivera

Laguna State Polytechnic University – Philippines